

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7830067>

Raximbayev Xursand Fayzulla o'g'li

Abstract : *Dystopian literature is a type of speculative fiction that depicts the future. Dystopias are society in terminal decline, with characters battling environmental disaster, technology domination, and government persecution.*

Key words : *human misery, squalor, oppression, disease, overcrowding, environmental destruction, war.*

Introduction

The dystopian literary genre is concerned with stories about an unfair society in which people's quality of life decreases as a result of deprivation, tyranny, or terror. Because these stories are typically set in the future, they are frequently indicative of current societal issues pushed to their logical conclusion. The concept of dystopia arose in direct contrast to the concept of utopia, which represents an ideal society of peace, harmony, and equality. Some dystopian authors create an ostensibly idyllic scenario only to show it to be covertly dystopian. Dystopian writing is common in science fiction (many stories incorporate scientific or technical breakthroughs) and, by extension, speculative fiction, which includes any literature dealing with fantastical and future aspects. Politics and religion are frequently used as criticism on real-life historical events by dystopian writers. Parallels to modern society sometimes include forewarnings of disastrous repercussions. Dystopian fiction frequently depicts an unfavourable future caused by humanity itself.

Historical Context

Several cautionary stories of unwise actions leading to disastrous outcomes have been written throughout history. Researchers couldn't help but think about the likelihood of immorality triumphing over morality. Several people took it upon themselves to solve the problem by providing alternative remedies. One of the earliest responses to the threat of immorality came from English philosopher Thomas More, who in his 1516 work *Utopia* proposed a solution to the ills of contemporary European society.

More defined a utopian society as one of peace, dignity, tolerance, equality, and overall harmony in all human activity. Three hundred years later, English philosopher Jeremy Bentham would respond to More's ideas with what he called *cacotopia* (the prefix *caco-* meaning "worst")—a poorly managed society plagued with dishonesty and servitude. The phrase later developed into *dystopia*, which means "evil" in Greek and was created in 1868 by English philosopher John Stuart Mill.

Several academics used satire to mock utopian beliefs, which spawned dystopian literature. Instead of attempting to create an ideal form of society, as utopian literature did, dystopian texts imagined a future in which society tragically paid for its negligence.

Writers typically express anti-utopian sentiments as a direct response to the contemporary society in which they live, much like More did when constructing his Utopia. Other works featured a cautionary message, indicating that if the real-world societal constructions represented in the narrative were allowed to continue, they would ultimately lead to a dystopian future.

As writers became more critical of culture in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, the quantity of dystopian books increased. From the 1930s to the 1960s, some of the most significant dystopian literature was produced, and it was inspired by political and social situations such as the impact of industrial technology, totalitarianism in Nazi Germany and the Stalinist Soviet Union, and advances in nuclear weaponry. The Nazi and Stalinist governments of the 1940s and 1950s provided significant inspiration for dystopian authors of the time. Some of the genre's most significant works are influenced by repressive governmental systems.

Worries about the industrial revolution and expanding technology were expressed in the writings of H.G. Wells, Aldous Huxley, and George Orwell, who imagined worlds in which machinery was harmful to human nature. Whilst writers continued to build on the implications of events such as governmental corruption and nuclear war, they also began to shift the emphasis away from the technological element of industry and towards the environmental effect of people and depleting natural resources. Dystopian literature flourished in the late twentieth century, with popular fiction writers such as Margaret Atwood and Cormac McCarthy spinning their own modern tales of dystopia.

Literary Themes

Political oppression is the most prominent theme in dystopian fiction. Several of the most notable dystopian writings, like Huxley's *Brave New World* (1931), Orwell's *Nineteen Eighty-Four* (1949), and Ray Bradbury's *Fahrenheit 451*, are centred on political turmoil (1953). Dystopian universe rulers are frequently ruthless and despotic, generating a need for rebellion, which is generally begun or expanded by the work's protagonist. An emphasis on politics is typically a satirical response to a real-world political situation that the author views potentially calamitous. Politics also extends into the economic themes of many dystopian literature, where class struggle has resulted in a clear division between the affluent and the poor, and individuals are required to follow strict government policies.

Many dystopian books have religious elements, with tyrants using religious ideas to exert dominance over the population. Atwood's *The Handmaid's Tale* (1986), Huxley's *Brave New World*, and, in certain ways, Yevgeny Zamyatin's *Us* (1924), which employs many parallels to depict organised religion, are all important works of fiction featuring

religious dictatorship. Each novel confronts the reader with a civilization ruled by an extreme dogmatic organisation that manipulates faith to coerce conformity.

Another common theme in dystopian literature is nature's rebellion against humanity. For many years, conservation of the Earth's natural resources has been a major concern.

This knowledge has frequently been exploited as a story technique by dystopian authors, bringing exploitation of nature to such an extreme that it culminates in mankind's ruin. Other works employ the concept of nature in a different way, with oppressors forbidding contact with nature in order to further discourage interest in things beyond their domain and maintain more control over society.

Major works and authors

Jonathon Swift's 1726 masterpiece *Gulliver's Travels* is one of the oldest examples of dystopian fiction. Though most people do not instantly associate this story with dystopian themes, Swift wrote it as a satire on modern society. At the end, he includes a dystopian twist in which Gulliver discovers that humans are no better than the barbaric Yahoos he saw on his travels. The dystopian paradigm evolved further in 1872 with Samuel Butler's *Erewhon*, which introduced the concept of machines obtaining awareness and so being a threat to society—a topic that has recurred in several dystopian works. By the late 1800s, novelists like Wells were putting their own touch on the dystopian environment. His novella *The Time Machine* (1895) not only satirised Victorian society's ill habits, but it also dealt with the ramifications of futuristic technology. Wells was a key player in the creation of dystopian literature as one of the genre's early authors.

Brave New World by Aldous Huxley was a keystone in the dystopian universe.

Huxley's story foresees a future in which individuals are replicated by technology. Human feeling and intimacy are therefore gone, and societal harmony is predicated on a tight class system. This technology is also used to brainwash society into believing that this way of life is correct and correct. Huxley's story, inspired by the industrial revolution's rising consumer culture, compares life to an assembly line. In his day, mass-produced, throwaway commodities were becoming prevalent. Everyone in Huxley's novel are members of a World State that worships Henry Ford, the entrepreneur who popularised the assembly line business model.

In the 1940s, Orwell wrote numerous important dystopian stories, notably *Animal Farm* (1945), an allegorical novel about a gang of revolutionary farm animals reflecting Communist Russia's political corruption. He proceeded to express his disgust with Stalinism in the 1949 classic *Nineteen Eighty-Four*, which is sometimes linked to Aldous Huxley's *Brave New World*. Orwell focuses on the threat of pervasive government control and was heavily influenced by Stalinist policies of the time, with the omnipresent Big Brother and Thought Police symbolising the Soviet Union's dictatorship and secret police.

The Handmaid's Tale by Margaret Atwood is set in a dystopian country controlled by a Christian theocracy. In Atwood's story, a state is ruled by a religious organisation that oppresses women. Atwood, an enthusiastic feminist, imagined a world in which the feminist movement had failed and women were essentially reproductive vessels governed by the affluent male elite.

Conclusion

Nonetheless, when authors write dystopian writings, they seek to convey an essential message about society to the audience. Many dystopian novels may appear to be fantasies since they discuss the future, but readers should be aware that, through time, dystopian novels have gained reality in many topics. The authors want to show the world what horrific things we are capable of if we allow corruption to take over our government and lives. Dystopian novels may exaggerate, but when you think about it, those "fantasies" aren't that far off the mark.

REFERENCES:

1. Girard, Greg (1993). *City of Darkness: Life in Kowloon Walled City*. ISBN 9781873200131.
2. ^ Rusen, Jorn; Rösen, Jörn; Fehr, Michael; Rieger, Thomas (2005). *Thinking Utopia: Steps Into Other Worlds*. Berghahn Books. ISBN 978-1-57181-440-1.
3. ^ Jump up to: a b "Definition of "dystopia"". Merriam-Webster. Merriam-Webster, Inc. 2012.
4. ^ Jump up to: a b "Definition of "dystopia"". Oxford Dictionaries. Oxford University Press. 2012. Archived from the original on 14 May 2013.
5. ^ "Dystopia - Examples and Definition of Dystopia as a Literary Device". *Literary Devices*. 6 July 2021. Retrieved 1 October 2021.
6. ^ "Utopia vs. Dystopia" (PDF). Okanogan School District.
7. ^ "The Fine Line between Utopia and Dystopia | The Prolongation of Work". *sites.williams.edu*. Retrieved 1 October 2021.
8. ^ "Dystopias & Utopias: Dystopias". Miami Dade College Learning Resources.
9. ^ Read Write Think (2006). "Dystopias: Definition and Characteristics" (PDF). Read Write Think. Archived (PDF) from the original on 23 September 2010.
10. ^ Younger, Lewis Henry (1747). *Utopia: Or, Apollo's Golden Days*. George Faulkner.
11. ^ Tisdall, Nigel (4 November 2016). "Postcard from Belgium: the birthplace of utopia". *Financial Times*. Retrieved 28 August 2018.
12. ^ Mill, John Stuart (1988). *Public and parliamentary speeches – Part I – November 1850 – November 1868*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press. ISBN 0-415-03791-3. Retrieved 16 February 2015.